

The Role of Women in *Saṁskāras* in the Vedic Age: A historical perspective

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Abstract: The research paper explores the role of women in the performance of *Saṁskāras* during the vedic period. The *Saṁskāra* occupies a vital place in the socio-religious framework of ancient Indian culture. These rites of passage were designed to purify, refine and prepare an individual for different stages of life, beginning from conception and continuing until death. Though rooted in vedic tradition and elaborated in later texts like *Grhyasūtras* and *Manusmṛti*, *Saṁskāras* played a dual role as both sacred rituals and instruments for shaping social order and moral values. Through a historical lense, the author aims to critically examine the participation of women in the performance of *saṁskāras* through an analysis of Vedic texts, including the *Atharvaveda* as well as *Dharmasūtra* and *Smṛti* literature.

Keywords: Women, *Saṁskāra*, *Grhyasūtras*, historical perspective.

1. Introduction

“प्रकृतिपुरुषात्मकं जगत्” i.e. The Universe is composed of *Prakṛti* and *Puruṣa* – from this, it is understood that this universe has two important components. “अग्निषोमात्मकं जगत्”- it also reflects that cosmic processes are based on the dual principles of *Agni* and *Soma*. *Agni* is considered as *Puruṣa* while *Soma* represents as *Prakṛti*. The world is manifested through their union. Just as *Prakṛti* cannot exist without *Puruṣa*, similarly the feminine cannot exist without the masculine. They together sustain the continuity of the world. The *Smṛtisāstras* also explain that Supreme Brahman, though one, manifests itself into two forms, namely male and female. It is said in the *Manusmṛti* –

“द्विधा कृत्वाऽत्मनो देहमर्धेन पुरुषो अभवत् ।
अर्धेन नारी तस्यां स विराजम् असृजत् प्रभुः ॥”¹

Therefore, it cannot be said that women are inferior to men in terms of virtues or cultural refinement. Indeed, the progress of human society depends upon the equal participation of both men and women. No society can prosper by ignoring or disrespecting women. This idea is also expressed in the famous verse –

“यत्र नार्यस्तु पूज्यन्ते रमन्ते तत्र देवताः ।
यत्रैतास्तु न पूज्यन्ते सर्वास्तत्राफलाः क्रियाः ॥”²

From the study of Vedic literature, it is clear that during the Vedic period women enjoyed a high and respected position. Women played an important role in every sphere of life. In Indian tradition, life has four stages – 1. *Brahmacārya* (Student life), 2. *Grhastha* (Householder) 3. *Vānaprastha* (Retirement) and 4. *Sannyāsa* (Renunciation) and women were given equal importance comparable to men. From the stage of conception and throughout life, various *saṁskāras* (sacraments) were performed in Indian culture for both men and women. Though the *Dharmaśāstras* generally do not prescribe the *upanayana saṁskāra* for women but during the Vedic period, performance of women’s *upanayana* ceremony is found. In the *Atharvaveda*³, it is clearly mentioned that there is the practice of the performance of *upanayana saṁskāra* for women. The *Dharmasūtrakāras* expressed that the *Dvija* had the right to receive this sacrament. So it can be considered that *Brāhmaṇa* women, *Kṣatriya* women and *Vaiśya* women were also included in the *Dvija* section of people. So, it can be said that women too were entitled to

Samskāras. However, certain variations can be observed in the performance of the *samskāras*.

According to *Manusmṛti*⁴ only in the marriage sacrament the recitation of the Vedic mantras is performed while the other *samskāras* were performed in a simplified form without the chanting of Vedic mantras. ‘वयं सर्वे अमृतस्य पुत्राः’ - Following this Vedic tradition, every human being should have the right to receive *samskāras*.

2. *Samskāras*

The *Dharmaśāstra* tradition records numerous *samskāras*. For instance the *Manusmṛti*⁵ enumerates thirteen *samskāras*, while other authorities like *Vyāsa* mentions sixteen, *Yājñavalkya* twelve, *Viṣṇu* ten, the *Samskāra-Prakāśa* twenty-one, *Gautama* forty, *Baudhāyana* thirteen and *Āśvalāyana* also prescribes thirteen. The principal *samskāras* are enumerated as follows –

1. *Garbhādhāna* 2. *Pūmsavana* 3. *Sīmantonnyana* 4. *Jātakarma* 5. *Nāmakaraṇa* 6. *Niṣkramaṇa* 7. *Annaprāśana* 8. *Cūḍākarāṇa* 9. *Karṇavedha* 10. *Vidyārambha* 11. *Upanayana* 12. *Vedārambha* 13. *Keśānta* 14. *Samāvartana* 15. *Vivāha* and 16. *Antyeṣṭi*.

2.1 *Jātakarma Samskāra for women*

In the Vedic tradition, parents used to pray for long life of their children. There was no discrimination between son and daughter. The great sage *Bharadvāja* an ancient sage in Indian tradition, performed all the birth rites for his daughter. In the *Mahābhārata*⁶ –

“तस्यास्तु जातकर्मादि कृत्वा सर्वं तपोधनः ।
नमा चास्याः स कृतवान् भरद्वाजो महामुनिः ॥
श्रुतावतीति धर्मात्मा देवर्षिगणसंसदि ।
स्वे च तामाश्रमे न्यस्य जगाम हिमवद्वनम् ॥”

A study of Vedic *samskāras* reveals that the girls were also entitled to perform the *Jātakarma samskāra*.

2.2 *Nāmakaraṇa Samskāra for women*

In ancient practice, naming conventions were in practice according to *Varnadharmā Manusmṛti* prescribes that names assigned *Brāhmaṇas* should be auspicious, those of *Kṣatriyas* should denote strength and valour, *Vaiśyas* names should suggest wealth and *Śudras* names are expected to convey modesty.

A special consideration was accorded to the naming of females. The names are expected to be euphonious, easily pronounceable, semantically meaningful and auspicious.

The *Mahābhārata* illustrates the practice of *Nāmakaraṇa* rite as observed in the account of king *Drupada* who performed *nāmakaraṇa samskāra* for his daughter⁷. However, the *Āśvalāyana Gr̥hyasūtra* denotes that the *nāmakaraṇa* rite for girls was performed without the recitation of the Vedic mantras. Thus, the *nāmakaraṇa* rite was an established rite for female within the Vedic culture framework, it was marked by certain ritual differentiations.

2.3. *Niṣkramaṇa Samskāra for women :*

According to *Manusmṛti* and *Yājñavalkyasmṛti*, the *niṣkramaṇa samskāra* is prescribed to perform in the fourth month following a child's birth. It is also called as *Suryadarśana samskāra* in the *Vyāsasmṛti*. Both male and female children are regarded as equally eligible for the performance of this rite. It is prescribed in the *Manava Gr̥hyasūtra* that the father conducts the ceremony by presenting the child to the Sun while reciting a benedictory that invokes blessings of longevity, vitality

and prosperity.

“नमस्तेऽस्तु भगवन् शतरश्मे तमोनुद ।
जहि मे देव दौर्भाग्यं सौभाग्येन मां संयोजयस्व ॥”⁸

Thus, the *niṣkramaṇa saṃskāra* is regarded as equally applicable to female and male children.

2.4. *Annaprāsana Saṃskāra* for Women:

According to *Smṛtikāras*, *Annaprāsana* is to be performed in the month of six after birth for both male and female children. In the Vedic culture, this *saṃskāra* is prescribed for all children irrespective of gender. However, certain distinctions are observed in practice. For male children, the rite is performed in the sixth, eighth or tenth month, whereas for female children, the prescribed months are seventh, ninth or eleventh.

In the *Atharvaveda*, it is found that the *Annaprāsana* should be performed at the time of the eruption of the child's teeth⁹.

2.5. *Cūdākarāṇa Saṃskāra* for Women:

This *saṃskāra* is prescribed to perform in the first or third year for both male and female children. This rite involves the cutting of the hair that has grown since birth. This *saṃskāra* is also called *Caulakarma*. *Āśvalāyana Gṛhyasūtra*¹⁰ prescribed the performance of this rite for the girls without chanting the vedic mantras. Again it is said by *Hārīta* that

“स्त्रीशूद्रौ शिखां छित्त्वा क्रोधो वैराम्यतोऽपि वा ।
प्राजापत्यं प्रकुर्यातां निष्कृतिर्नान्यथा भवेत् ॥”¹¹

2.6. *Upanayana Saṃskāra* for Women:

According to the *Manusmṛti*, the eligibility for *Upanayana saṃskāra* is restricted to the *dvija* (twice born) classes, namely *Brāhmanas*, *Kṣatriyas* and *Vaiśyas*. The *śūdras* are not entitled to the performance of this rite. Although the women are not explicitly included within the *dvija* classification, the texts do not uniformly impose a prohibition against their participation. According to the *Vaśiṣṭha Dharmasūtra*, distinctions such as the *Gāyatri*, *Trīṣṭhubh* and *Jagati* metres were symbolically associated with the three *dvija varṇas*¹². *Atharvaveda* mentioned that woman gets worth husband through the disciplined observance of *Brahmacārya* - “ब्रह्मचर्येण युवानं विन्दते पतिम् ।”

After the performance of *Upanayana saṃskāra*, a boy is designated as *Brahmacārīn*. In early Vedic Society, girls too were admitted the discipline of *Brahmacārya*. Two categories of women are described in this context: the *Brahmavādinī* and the *Sadyovadhū*. The woman who undertakes vedic study and observes the disciplines associated with *Brahmacārya* is called *Brahmavādinī* and the woman who does not pursue prolonged vedic study and her *upanayana* is performed proximate to the time of marriage. It is also found in *Saṃskāramayukha* and *Smṛticandrikā* that the *Dharmasūtrakāra Hārīta*, explicitly mentions about two types of women *Brahmavādinī* and *Sadyovadhū*. The first type was the ascetic type who carried on the quest of truth, knowledge and spiritual pursuits for her ideal and the second one the *Sadyovadhū* was the domestic type who dedicated herself to the welfare of the family though there was no rigid opposition between the two. In Vedic period, great importance was attached to a girl's education. As a matter of fact, as many as thirty two women were supposed to be the *Ṛṣikās* of some of the hymns of the *Rgveda*. Some women who remained unmarried in the quest of truth, knowledge and scholarship were called *Brahmavādinīs*. The

Gr̥hyasūtra literature further corroborates this by prescribing that a maiden, upon attaining maturity, should be married after the performance of *upanayana* and the recitation of appropriate mantras.

2.7. *Samāvartana Saṃskāra* for Women:

In the Vedic culture, the *Samāvartana Saṃskāra* was entitled for women after the completion of the studentship. It is said in the *Āśvalāyana Gr̥hyasūtra* that after salving his two hands with ointment a *Brāhmaṇa* should salve his head first, a *Rājanya* his two arms, a *Vaiśya* the belly, a woman should salve her secret parts and a person who gain their livelihood by running should salve their thighs. *Hārta* mentioned that women's *Samāvartana* should be performed before — “प्राग्रजसः समावर्त्तनमिति”

2.8. *Vivāha Saṃskāra* for women:

“अयज्ञो वै पुरुषः योऽपत्नीकः”¹³ i.e. man without a wife is considered unfit for the performance of social and religious duties. This view is extensively discussed in the *Mahābhārata*, *Smṛti* literature and *Purāṇas*. A man without progeny does not attain the desired spiritual realms; therefore for the attainment of higher worlds, it is deemed necessary for him accept a wife. In performance of the major sacrifices, the role of *Patnī* is an indispensable part. The grammarian *Pāṇini* is also supporting this view by citing “पत्युर्नो यज्ञसंयोगे”.¹⁴ Similarly, the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* and other Vedic sources affirm that a man cannot achieve ritual completeness without a wife. This idea is further reinforced by the statement, “अधो ह वा एष आत्मनः यत् पत्नी”¹⁵.

Furthermore, it is asserted that marriage itself functions as the Vedic initiation (*upanayana*) for women. The commentator *Medhātithi* states that, “विवाह एव स्त्रीणां वैदिकसंस्कारोपनयनम्”¹⁶ This ritual includes the recitation of various mantras by women. After the kindling of the sacred fire, the father as the giver of the bride, presents the ornamented bride to the groom. At this juncture, the bride and groom recite the following mantra —

“ओं समञ्जन्तु विश्वे देवाः समापो हृदयानि नौ |
सं मातरिश्वा सं धाता समुद्देश्ठी दधातु नौ ॥”¹⁷

Again it is observed that during the marriage ritual, the groom sits facing east, while the bride sits to his right. Then the bride recites the following mantra –

“ओं प्रमे पतियानः पन्थाः कल्पतां शिवाः अरिष्ठा पतिलोकं गमेयत् ॥”¹⁸

Thus in the Marriage *saṃskāra*, women are seen to have an important and active role.

2.9. *Antyeṣṭisaṃskāra* for women:

Within the framework of life-cycle rituals women, like men occupy a significant role. Accordingly, upon the death of a woman, the *Antyeṣṭisaṃskāra* is to be performed in a prescribed and orderly manner. In the *Antyeṣṭisaṃskāra* the husband performed the rituals and also the wife has the right to perform the *Antyeṣṭisaṃskāra*. Thus, her role is not merely symbolic and ritually significant within the funeral context.

In the *Mahābhārata Yudhiṣṭhira* is said to have performed the funeral rites of *Karṇa* alongwith *Karṇa*'s wife in accordance with *dharma*.

“स ताभिः सह धर्मात्मा प्रेतकृत्यमनन्तरम् |
चकार विधिवद् धीमान् धर्मराजो युधिष्ठिरः ॥”¹⁹

Furthermore, *Yudhiṣṭhira* along with *Draupadi* is described as performing the

funeral rites for *Droṇa*, *Karṇa* and other eminent persons as well as their sons.

“युधिष्ठिरस्तु द्रोणस्य कर्णस्य च महात्मनः
धृष्टद्युम्नाभिमन्युभ्यां हैडिम्बस्य च राक्षसः |
विराटप्रभृतीनां च सुहृदामुपकरणाम्
द्रुपद-द्रौपदेयानां द्रौपद्या सहितो ददौ ॥”²⁰

Pāraskara Gr̥hyasūtra also prescribed that a married female should perform the rites for her husband and his relatives – “प्रत्तानामितरे कुर्वीस्”²¹, “ताश्च तेषाम्”²²

In the *Dharmasindhu* it is said that –

“सर्वाभावे स्वयं पत्न्यः स्वभृतृणाममंत्रकम्
सपिण्डीकरणं कुर्युस्ततः पार्वणामेव च ॥”²³

From such textual evidences, it may be inferred that women, like men possess the right to participate in the *Antyeṣṭisamskāra*.

Conclusion

In the vedic period women held a respected and significant position in society and were actively included in the religious and cultural framework of life. The philosophical foundation of the Universe as a union of *Prakṛti* (feminine) and *Puruṣa* (masculine) itself establishes the idea of equality rather than hierarchy. Evidences from texts like the *Manusmṛiti*, *Atharvaveda*, *Dharmasūtras* and *Gr̥hyasūtras* show that women were entitled to many *samskāras* from conception to funeral rites. In early Vedic tradition, even *Upanayana* and Vedic education were accessible to women, especially in the form of *Brahmavādinī*. Women participated in important rituals, and in some cases, even recited mantras, though later texts sometimes prescribed simplified forms without Vedic chanting. Thus it can be concluded that women in the Vedic age were not excluded but were integral participants in religious life, enjoying rights and recognition comparable in many respects to men. The later limitations seen in ritual practices are historical developments rather than original Vedic norms.

Endnotes

1. Ma.Sa. I.32
2. Ibid.3.56
3. Ath.Ved. 11.5
4. Man.Sm.II.66-67
5. Ibid. II.16,26,29 &III.1-4
6. Mah. Shalya, 49, 64-65
7. Mah. Adi..166.54
8. Ma.Gr.Sū.1.19.4
9. Ath.Ve. 6.140
10. Āś.G. 1/17-18
11. nirnayasindhu. 3 chapter, p.no- 190
12. Vas.Dh.4.3
13. Tai. Br. 2/2/2/6
14. Pāṇ.4.1.13
15. Tai.Brā. 3.3.3.5
16. Medh.2.67
17. R.V.10/85/47, Pā.Gr.Sū. 1/4/14
18. M. Brā. 2/1/8
19. Ma.Str.27/28
20. Ibid.Sān. 42.3-4
21. Pār.Gr. 3.10.42

22. Ibid. 3.10.43
23. Dharmasindhu. III.

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